

More on the gold band jumping spider *Thyene natalii* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae)

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Abstract: The gold band jumping spider *Thyene natalii* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 has a wide distribution in Africa and is known from Ethiopia in the north to South Africa in the south. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens with notes on their agrobiont behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Thyene* Simon, 1886 is represented by 52 species and subspecies of which 37 species are known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2023). So far, 14 species have been recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Most of these species have been recorded during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). One of the *Thyene* species commonly sampled was identified as *Thyene natalii* Peckham & Peckham, 1903.

Thyene natalii was described from Durban in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. This species is the only *Thyene* that has a short ovoid abdomen with an abdominal pattern composed of transverse bands. The aim of this paper is to provide more information on the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens. Their agrobiont behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa are discussed.

TAXONOMY

Thyene natalii Peckham & Peckham, 1903

Thyene strandi Caporiacco, 1939: 376 (Ethiopia).

Thyene natalii Peckham & Peckham, 1903: 227 (South Africa); Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009: 85 (Zimbabwe) (Synonym of *Thyene strandi*); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010 (South Africa).

Thyene natali Lessert, 1936: 294 (Mozambique); Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008: 216 (Zimbabwe); Dawidowicz & Wesolowska 2016: 461 (Kenya).

Description: Female body size 6–7 mm (Figs 1–2). Carapace fawn; cephalic region with layer white setae and decorated with five irregular black spots; anterior eye region with white setae; eyes circled with white scales; a cluster of black tufts of setae behind anterior posterior eyes. Abdomen ovoid; same colour as carapace; dorsally decorated with transverse bands that vary from silver to gold to brown and white iridescent scales (Figs 7–10). Legs the same colour as carapace; femur I marked, on the front face, with thin rows of dark lines, which are repeated, with less distinctness, on the femur of the second leg. Epigyne is weakly sclerotised, with small anteriorly placed depression (Figs 9–12).

Male body size 5–7 mm. (Figs 3–4): Cephalic region dark brown with a wide band of white setae around the sides and back; pale yellowish-brown band on upper sides and across the anterior thoracic part. Eye region with gold and silver iridescent scales; face marked with three lines of reddish scales that run around below the lateral eyes onto the thoracic part; rings of red setae around median eyes; tufts of black hairs behind the lateral eyes.

Figures 1–2. *Thyene natalii* female. 1. Habitus dorsal view. 2. Anterior view
Photo credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Johan van Zyl.

Abdomen ovoid; dark with faint transverse bands of red and silvery iridescent scales. Legs: first leg robust; femora patellae and metatarsi of all legs dark, rest of legs banded. Palp brown, bulb rounded, embolus very long, encircling the bulb more than three times (Figs 5–6).

Figures 3–8. *Thyene natalii*. 3. Male habitus dorsal view. 4. Male eye pattern anterior view. 5–6. Male palp. 7–8. Epigyne. Photo credits: 3–4. Rudi Steenkamp. 5 & 7. ASD. 6 & 8. After Wesolowska & Cumming (2008).

Figures 9–12. *Thyene natalii* female showing the variation in abdominal color pattern. Photo credits: 9–11. Vida vd Walt. 12. Rudi Steenkamp.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Eswatini, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Map 1)

Eastern Cape: Addo Citrus Research Station (-33.55, 25.69); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Keurkloof district, Ferndale Farm (-33.68, 24.83); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Bathurst (-34.20, 24.7083). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); 15 km N Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

Limpopo: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Balloon (-24.17, 30.25); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Tshulu (-22.58, 30.81); Zanzibar Border Post -22.57, 28.45). Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.320, 29.324). **Mpumalanga:** Burger's Hall (-25.08, 31.06); Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit district, Brondal Farm (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit district, Glenwood Farm (-29.87, 30.98); Plaston (-25.34, 31.06); Schagen (-25.43, 30.80). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Riebeeck-West (-33.34, 18.86); Grabouw (-34.14, 19.04); Wellington (-33.65, 19.00); Knysna (-34.03, 23.03); Ruitersbos (-33.94, 22.05); Sedgfield (-34.03, 22.81).

Map 1. known distribution of *Thyene natalii* in South Africa

LIFESTYLE

In South Africa *T. natalii* was collected from foliage of shrubs and trees from all the floral biomes except in the more arid biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They make retreats with silk threads between leaves. The species was also sampled on the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* (fever trees) in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad, 2016).

It was collected from several agroecosystems such as avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001a, b), and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) and is identified as one of South Africa's agrobiont species.

In macadamia orchards, spiders were collected over a 12-month period (July 1997–June 1998) from three orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa using dichlorvos as a knock-down spray (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001a).

Figure 13. Seasonal fluctuation of *Thyene natalii* in three macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld, South Africa (After Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001a).

Of the 2778 spiders collected, 73% belonged to the Salticidae, represented by 17 species with *T. natalii* (394 specimens) the second most abundant species representing 30% of all the spiders collected from macadamia. It was recorded throughout the year from the three orchards in Mpumalanga (Fig. 13). The numbers peaked in February, April, and September. Of the specimens recorded females represent 41%, males 37% and juveniles 22% (Fig. 14) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001b).

In two avocado orchards in Mpumalanga, of all the spiders collected over a year period, two *Thyene* species *T. natalii* and *T. coccineovittata* represented 22.5% of the total number of spiders sampled. A total of 405 *T. natalii* specimens were sampled, representing 11 % of all spiders sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005).

AGGRESSIVE MIMICRY

While sorting the spiders sampled from different Macadamia orchards, we came across a few dead Mediterranean fruit flies *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Figs 14–15). The fly, commonly also known as medflies, is native to sub-Saharan Africa and it has no near relatives in the Western Hemisphere. It is one of the most destructive fruit pests in the world.

T. natalii (Figs 16–17) resembled the medflies closely. They both have dark spots on the cephalothorax and similar horizontal bands on the abdomen. Even the lines on the front legs of the spider resemble the lines on the wings of the fly. This might be aggressive mimicry that suggests *T. natalii* prey on the fruit flies.

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Figures 14–15. Dorsal view of adult male Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann). Photo credits Katja (iNaturalist).

Figures 16–18. Adult female *Thyene natalii*. 16–17. Dorsal view. 18. Anterior view. Photo credits 16–17. Peter Webb. 18. Vida vd Walt.

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